

Screening of rice for resistance to tungro virus

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The incidence of tungro virus disease has been high in rice planted in late August or early September in Sambalpur district, Orissa. Tungro has been observed in the area since 1972. At the Regional Research Station, 980 varieties and lines were field-screened for tungro resistance during the 1976 kharif season (Nov.). A high buildup of green leafhopper *Nephotettix*

virescens coincided with high disease incidence. Twenty-nine varieties were rated as resistant and 85 as moderately resistant (see table). Tall varieties and lines that were resistant were ARC 7318, ARC 10531, ARC 13560, ARC 13820, ARC 13901, ARC 13959, ARC 7110, and Boroshungha. Semidwarf rices with resistance were IR2307-486-5-3, IR2797-125-3-2-2, RP938-27, Amol 1-82, BR 167-2B-9, BR 4 (BR 51-91-6), BR 1014 B-Pn-18-1-4, 153/54, TNAU 13610, RP 744-180-1-1-2, RP 975-109-2, 4154, CR 202-22-527, MR 292-2, and R 35-2750.

rices except Pusa 33 and the length of the plumule was reduced in all but Monohar sali (see table).

In another test, seedlings of IR8, Monohar sali, and MR 1550-5-157 were inoculated at 4 days after germination by the above method. Average room temperature varied from 28° to 34°C. Brownish lesions developed on the radicles of 5% of the seedlings of Monohar sali and on 2% of the IR8 and MR 1550-5-157 seedlings. It seems that *R. oryzae* does not significantly affect germination of rice seed, but may occasionally occur on radicles and cause seedlings to decay.

Tungro screening results in the 1976 kharif season. Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Orissa, India.

Source of material	Total screened	Varieties and lines (no.)	
		Resistant	Moderately resistant
International Rice Observational Nursery	331	15	68
International Rice Tungro Nursery	183	8	7
National Screening Nursery (India)	394	6	10

Reaction of rice varieties to and yield losses from sheath rot

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A field trial in 1976 determined the reactions of 16 popular rice varieties to sheath rot disease caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*. The varieties were spray inoculated when they were 80 days old. Control plots were maintained for each variety. The yields of both healthy and infected plants of each variety were recorded and the percentage of yield loss was determined (see table).

Reaction of rice varieties to and yield loss from sheath rot. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)	Yield loss (%)
Co 39	48.6	57.4
Co 36	34.0	48.0
Karuna	31.8	39.8
Kannagi	31.4	33.4
Jaya	29.1	42.3
Vaigai	25.8	29.8
IR20	22.6	31.4
Kanchi	21.7	28.1
IR22	19.3	22.4
IR8	19.2	28.5
Ponni	17.1	17.3
IR29	15.3	21.2
IR5	14.2	24.3
Bhavani	12.7	13.9
Jagannath	3.6	6.2

Effect of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* on germination of rice

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Rhynchosporium oryzae, the cause of leaf scald, usually produces symptoms on older leaves. Manifestations of its attack on seed germination and germinating

seedlings were studied at AAU, Jorhat. Seeds of six rice cultivars (see table) were surface sterilized, kept on moist filter paper in petri dishes, and sprayed with a spore suspension of the fungus (10^5 conidia/ml). The percentage of germination was reduced after 4 days of inoculation, but the differences disappeared 2 days later except in Pusa 2-21 and MR 1550-5-157. The length of the radicle was reduced in all

Effect of *R. oryzae* on seed germination and germinating seedlings of six rice varieties. Assam Agricultural University, India.

Cultivar	Germination (%)		Length of radicle (mm)		Length of plumule (mm)	
	Uninoculated	Inoculated	Uninoculated	Inoculated	Uninoculated	Inoculated
Pusa 2-21	91	94	33.9	23.9	19.2	14.5
MR 1550-5-157	90	94	18.9	11.1	5.7	3.8
IR8	94	89	40.2	35.9	15.9	13.9
Prosadbhog	99	94	27.4	21.0	12.5	8.8
Pusa 33	97	90	29.0	36.5	11.8	9.5
Monohar sali	100	95	29.3	28.2	10.1	10.1